

VISHNUKUNDIN COINS-A STUDY

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The Vishnukundins ruled Andhradesa and parts of ancient Vidarbha during the 4th and 7th centuries A.D. In the post Satavahana period the Vishnukundins were powerful and exerted great influence in the central and eastern Deccan as Vakatakas in the Northern Deccan and Central India. This period is also noted as a period of economic change. Archaeologically the economic situation is best represented by the coins and currency system. The coinage of the Vishnukundins, next to the Satavahanas, stand out in importance. The Vishnukundins revived the Vedic religious practices and their copper plates and coins reveal their faith in both Vaishnavism and Saivism.

Based on the nine Copper plate grants and one Stone inscriptions of the Vishnukundins, the chronology of these kings has been reconstructed as follows: Indra Varma I(388-400 AD), Madhava Varma I(400-418 AD), Govinda Varma I(418-455 AD) Madava Varma II(455-490 AD), Deva Varma(490-493 AD), Madava Varma III(493-522 AD), Vikramendra Varma I(522-528AD), Indra Varma II (528-556 AD), Vikramendra Varma II(556-570 AD), Govinda Varma II (570-576AD), Madhava Varma IV (576-623AD), MachenaBhattaraka (623-624 AD).

ISSUERS OF THE COIN TYPES

The Lion x Temple issues appear to be the first among the Vishnukundin series issued by Madhavavarman II, the most powerful among the early Vishnukundin rulers, deserves to be credited as the herald of an independent coinage for the Vishnukundin Dynasty. The Lion was their lanchana as seen from the earliest seals, namely Tummalagudem plates of Govindavarman I and Velpuru pillar inscription of Madhavavarman II. Again, it was Madhavavarman II who altered the seal on the Ipur copper plates. Here the seal was divided in two sections by a horizontal line. The upper register depicted the Srivatsa in the centre, flanked by ploughs, and the legend Sri Madhavavarman was given in the lower register. It appears, therefore, that Madhavavarman II first innovated the coin devices by adopting the royal lanchhana, viz., "Lion with raised paw", from the seals and inscriptions and added the auspicious Srivatsa as the obverse device, while the plough, as depicted on the seal of the Ipur plates-I, formed part of the reverse in combination with the temple of Sri parvatasvamin, the deity of the Vishnukundivamsa from now onwards. We may also logically presume that the Lion x Temple type was standardised some time after the issue of Ipur-I, i.e., after 37th regnal year of Madhavavarman II.

The issue of the uninscribed Bull type, couchant or standing to right with chakra or conch on the reverse appear to have been initiated later. Vikramendra-bhattarakavarman II, after the consolidation of the northern territories under the influence of the Vakatakas and their close allies Bharasiva Nagas of Padmavati issued another coin-type based on the earlier local symbolism. These Bull type coins possess certain northern traits and differ from the Salankayana or early Pallava smaller issues weighting less, uninscribed Bull coins which were closer to the later Satavahana types from Kondapur. Bull appears as the lanchhana in the Tundi plates of Vikramendra-bhattarakavarman II., Uttamasraya. B.D. Chattopadhyaya, however, holds an opposite view, basing on Yelleswaram evidence and says that the Bull type coins are earlier and observes that the origin of Lion type coins can be put towards the end. The issuer of the Bull type, however is regarded as Vikramendravarman I.

Vikramendravarman I was Vishnukundi-Vakataka-vamsadvayalamkritajanman. It is almost certain that the region of Western Maharashtra-Vidarbha and Dakshina Kosala were under the Vishnukudin control during this period. Apart from inscriptional evidence, the coins afford a clear

picture. The ubiquitous evidence of coins of Lion x Temple type, Lion x conch or chakra, in sites as far as Nevasa, Paunar and others in the Vidarbha region, eastern Andhra sites, Telangana areas of Karimnagar-Nalgonda, and the latest from Keesaragutta besides Yelleswaramu and Nagarjunkonda clearly speak of the vast expanse of the dynasty. Likewise, the Bull type, standing or couchant, with the reverse conch or chakra have also indicated a wider distribution pattern. Occasionally both the varieties were together found at Paunar and other Vidarbha sites, also at Gurjala, Yelleswaramu etc. The temple device on the reverse was also seen rarely on some Bull type coins from Vidarbha and Prakasham district. The greater numbers and varieties are notably from the Vidarbha region rather than Andhra-Telangana.

M.Rama Rao has published a series of coins with variations. The coins of usual type with the legends ka and ra which represents the full name of Vikramendra. Coins from Paunar in Maharashtra show a new variation of this type. They have ornamented lion without the double "ya" symbol on the obverse and axle of a wheel as if viewed from the sides of the rivers. R.Subramanyam reported coins from Gurjala and Yelleswaramu with bull on the obverse and reverse a trident flanked by two lamp stands with a rayed circle. The legend kra ma or vikrama are read. They are attributed to Vikramendravarman. M. Rama Rao doubt this because bull was the crest of Pallavas. But then coins may be assigned to the Vishnukundins as a particular device might have continued despite the dynastic changes. Bull/Trident or Bull/Conch types are found in Vishnukundin area. The rayed circle motif is associated with this type. The continuity of this type in the eastern Chalukyan period in Andhra area shows its popularity. In Yelleswaramu excavation Vishnukundin layers yielded bull conch type along with lion and vase type. The legend (vikramendravarman) also support the attribution to Vishnukundins. Chronologically bull type coins might have been issued in 5th century while lion and vase type in a later series. Rama Rao attributed to Madhavavarman.

A large number of Vishnukundin coins has been reported from several sites in Deccan and Andhra. In connection with the present research paper, 960 Vishnukundin coins were studied which are collected from the AP State Archaeology and Museums which are found in Keesara Village, Rangareddy District, Tangudupalli, Vijayanagaramu District, Korukonda, East Godavari District, Revoor Village, Nalgonda District, Talukunta Village, Karimnagar District and other places.

A.P. State department of Archaeology and Museums has roughly 807 coins, but studied only 758 coins and other coins were distributed to all district museums and 146 coins collected from Birla Archaeological Cultural Research Institute, Hyderabad. Seven copper coins were found in the Srivari Hundi of Tirumala Tirupathi Devasthanams, Tirupathi. The above coins of Vishnukundins were prepared as a catalogue giving the coin data as a quantity which helped in the systematic study of the coins and currency system of the period. All the coins in the collection of the museums are without any legend and hence they cannot be ascribed to any individual rulers of this dynasty.

Importance of the study

In the evolution of Ancient Andhra coinage earliest to be used were for the punch marked coins which were first succeeded by uninscribed cast coins and later by the inscribed coins. The Sathavahana coins were issued from different parts of Deccan and these were made mostly of lead and some of potin, bronze, brass and copper. Very few portrait coins of some of the later Sathavahana rulers were made of silver and lead. Ikshvakus followed Sathavahanas and their coins are known from Nagarjunakonda excavations and Ongole treasure trove and these were made of lead.

Vishnukundins issued coins mostly made of copper with a core of iron and rarely used lead and potin for making these coins. The coins of the period between rule of Vishnukundin to that of Bahmani are very limited and majority of these coins are made of copper. Subsequent to the rule of Vishnukundins lead was not used in Andhradesa.

The important objective of the study is the economy of the period which shows great stimuli to agriculture and new areas were brought under cultivation. With the decline of Roman trade at the beginning of the fourth century A.D. the mercantile economy declined. However, the maritime trade contacts with the South East Asian countries from the Vengi region and the manufacturing of iron objects of military and domestic nature on large scale in the Nalgonda and Karimnagar districts sustained the economy of the period. Its trading area was wider i.e., the entire Deccan as in the case of the Satavahana period. While the exports were textiles and agrarian products, the imports included ivory objects, carnelian beads, intaglios and stamped pottery. The cultural products that were exported were Brahmanical and Buddhist images particularly from 3rd century onwards. Suvarnabhumi probably was an area of luxury trade with the east coast which supplied prestige goods. Another notable feature is that the Andhra Coast was integrated into wider looping trade system of the coast as well as indigenous maritime networks between the Arabian Peninsula, South East Asia or between the Indian sub-continent and China. Hence, the coinage of the Vishnukundins was continuous and sustained in each religion of the dynastic rule.

A cultural study of coins catalogued in this paper from the points of view of religious symbols, iconography, and technological developments would be highly rewarding exercise. The vase or purnakumba one of the eight auspicious symbols is found on the Vishnukundin coins. Its occurrence in early Indian Amaravathi and Nagarjuna konda sculpture is well known. A comparative study of the two would be useful. A large number of animals have been depicted on these coins. A typological classification of lion or elephant or other animals would add to our knowledge of the contemporary times.

The find spots of the coins useful to know the political boundaries of the Vishnukundins. Vishnukundins were confined to the Vengi region, situated between the Godavary in the north and the Krishna in the south, with occasionally extensions beyond these two rivers. But the provenance of the coins mentioned above indicates that the districts of Nalgonda and Karimnagar in the eastern half of Telangana were also included in the Vishnukundin kingdom.

Findings of the Study

The majority of vishnukundin coins have on the obverse a highly stylized lion with open mouth, upraised paw and uplifted tail and on the reverse a vase flanked by two vertical lamp stands-all within a rayed circle. These coins except very rarely do not contain any legend, and hence ascribing them to the Vishnukundins has been a controversial issue for a long time. Earlier, the coins with a lion symbol on the obverse were considered as Pallava coins. But a majority of scholars in recent years have veered round to the view that coins with lion and bull symbols on the obverse and a vase or kalasa with lamp-posts on either side, inside a rayed boarder, belong to Vishnukundins based on the find spots of these coins which are mostly in Telangana and North Andhra regions and not to its south. Vishnukundin inscriptions as well as the discovery of these coins in excavations such as Yeleswaramu in Nalgonda district prove the indentity of the coins. The lion type of coins are regarded as belonging to the earlier period of Vishnukundin rule. The lion probably symbolizes power and could be a dynastic symbol. Most scholars think that reverse symbol is a vase or kalasa on a pedestal with lamp posts on either side inside a rayed boarder, which probably contains water of life, stands for purity and fertility. Some reverse designs are not enclosed inside a rayed boarder. Some scholars consider that reverse design depicts a temple unit which is flanked by two ploughshares and a survey of large number of these coins reveals that this view is farfetched. As for the metal of these coins, it is interesting to note that Vishnukundins were the first to have used iron as a core material for their coins, which were coated with copper alloy at the top. Vishnukundins coins were made from ternary alloy consisting of copper, iron and tin, containing about 22% iron, 75.4% copper, 3 % tin.

The weights of 255 copper coins, Keesara village, Rangareddy District ranged between 1.09-8.69 grams and mean weight was 6.63 grams. The weights of 130 copper coins, Tangudupalli village, Vijayanagaramu district ranged between 0.64-11.96 grams and mean weight was 8.25 grams. The weights of 4 copper coins, Korukonda village, East Godavari district ranged between 2.76-4.71 grams and mean weight was 3.72 grams. The weights of 36 copper coins, Korukonda village, East Godavari district ranged between 2.81-5.31 grams and mean weight was 4.18 grams. The weights of 258 copper coins, Revoor village, Nalgonda village ranged between 2.1-13 grams and mean weight was 9.53 grams. The weights of 75 copper coins, Talukunta village, Karimnagar district ranged between 3.8-10.1 grams and mean weight was 7.45 grams. The weights of 7 copper coins, Srivari hundi, Tirumala Tirupathi Devasthanams, Tirupathi ranged between 7.01-9.14 grams and mean weight was 7.45 grams. It is obvious that the coins of various denominations were issued.

In this work, lowest weight (0.64 gms) coin found in Tangudupalli hoard, Vijayanagaramu district and highest weight (13 gms) found in Revoor village, Nalgonda district. In catalogued copper coins, the mean weight is in between 2.27 to 9.53. It shows Vishnukundins issued coins in different denominations and different weight standards. Coin data helped to know the economic change, economic situation and currency system during 4th and 6th century in Andhra under Vishnukundins. These Vishnukundin coins are great value for the study of ancient Indian Numismatics and history.

The find spots of the coins useful to know the economy system and political boundaries of the Vishnukundins. Vishnukundins were confined to the Vengi region, situated between the Godavary in the north and the Krishna in the south, with occasionally extensions beyond these two rivers. But the provenance of the coins mentioned above indicates that the districts of Nalgonda and Karimnagar in the eastern half of Telangana were also included in the Vishnukundin kingdom.

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